

Benzofurans from acetophenones by Claisen rearrangement

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Abstract : The condensation of acetophenones with propargylbromide in acetone-potassium carbonate medium yielded propargyloxyacetophenones which on thermal cyclisation leads to Claisen rearrangement to give 2-methylbenzofuran and 2,4-dimethyl benzodifurans.

Keywords : Claisen rearrangement, benzofuran, acetophenone.

Introduction

Natural as well as synthetic benzofurans are reported to have copious range of biological activities¹. In this communication, we report the synthesis of 2-methyl-4-hydroxy-5-acylbenzofurans and 2,5-dimethyl-8-acylbenzodifurans starting from the reaction between resacetophenone and respropiofenone with propargylbromide and subsequent Claisen rearrangement of the resulting propargyloxy-acetophenone/-propiofenone.

Results and discussion

The reaction of 2,4-dihydroxy-acetophenone/-propiofenone (1) with propargylbromide (2) in acetone potassium carbonate medium yielded 2'-hydroxy-4'-propargyloxy-acetophenone/-propiofenone (3a/b) and 2',4'-dipropargyloxy-acetophenone/-propiofenone (4a/b) in 90% and 88% yields respectively. The propargyloxy-acetophenones/-propiofenones when refluxed in polyethyleneglycol-200 (PEG) gave Claisen rearrangement products 2-methyl-4-hydroxy-5-acetylbenzofuran (5a/b) and 2,5-dimethyl-8-acetylbenzodifuran (6a/b) in good yield (Scheme 1). When the reaction was carried out with *N,N*-diethylaniline (NND) and tetrahydrofuran (THF), the yield of the cyclised end product was poor.

It is considered that 2-methylbenzofurans (5a/b and 6a/b) are formed by initial [3S,3S] sigmatropic rearrangement and enolisation followed by ring closure through ionic mechanism². In the present study, the potassium carbonate ionises the hydroxy group at C-2 of propargyl ether (3a/b and 4a/b) thereby facilitating the formation of 2-methylbenzofuran (5a/b and 6a/b).

Antimicrobial activity : All compounds were tested for antimicrobial activity against the bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* with DMF as solvent in 50, 100, 200 and 400 µg/ml concentrations by cup-plate diffusion method³ using gentamycin as standard drug. All the compounds showed moderate antimicrobial activities against the organisms at higher concentrations only.

Experimental

All the m.p.'s were uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer (Infrared model 337) spectrophotometer. The ¹H NMR spectra were recorded operating at 200 MHz on Varian Gemini spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard. Mass spectra were recorded at 70 eV on VG micro mass 7070-H instrument by direct inlet method.

Propargyloxy-acetophenones/-propiofenones (3a/b and 4a/b) : A mixture of potassium carbonate (0.362

Scheme 1

mol), propargylbromide (2) [(0.012 mol)/(0.024 mol)] and 2',4'-dihydroxyacetophenone (1a)/2',4'-dihydroxypropiophenone (1b) (0.01 mol) was refluxed in the dry acetone (200 ml) for 24/48 h on a water bath. Acetone was removed under vacuum and the crude residue was poured over crushed ice. The separated compounds were filtered under vacuum and recrystallised from petroleum ether (60–80°) to yield 3a/b and 4a/b as colourless flakes (Table 1).

Claisen rearrangement products of propargyloxyacetophenones/propiophenones (5a/b and 6a/b) : General procedure : A mixture of polyethyleneglycol 200 (150 ml) and 3/4 (0.01 mol) was refluxed at 235° C on an oil bath for 3 h. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into ice-cold water. The separated crude solids were filtered in vacuum and subjected to chromatography over silica gel (finer than 200 mesh) (10 g) to yield 5a/b and 6a/b (65–75%) as colourless solids (Table 1).

Table 1

Compd.	M.p. (°C)	IR ν_{\max} (cm ⁻¹)	NMR δ (ppm)	EIMS m/z (%)
3a	65	3211 (-OH), 2112 (C=C), 1620 (C=O)	1.91 (1H, t, J 6.5 Hz), 2.52 (3H, s), 4.82 (2H, d, J 7.5 Hz), 6.20 (1H, s), 6.43 (1H, d, J 9.5 Hz), 7.81 (1H, d), 10.75 (-OH) (D ₂ O exe)	-

Note

Table-1 (contd.)

3b	72	3215 (-OH), 2115 (C=C), 1620 (C=O)	1.21 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz), 1.91 (1H, t, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz), 2.92 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 6.5, 1 Hz), 4.81 (2H, t, <i>J</i> 7.5 Hz), 6.20 (1H, s), 6.43 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 9.5 Hz), 7.8 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 9.5 Hz), 10.75 (1H) (D ₂ O exe)	-
4a	78	3261 (-OH), 2114 (C=C), 1660 (C=O)	1.92 (2H, t, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz), 2.64 (3H, s), 4.65 (4H, t, <i>J</i> 7.5 Hz), 6.21 (1H, s), 6.62 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 9.5 Hz), 7.82 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 9.5 Hz)	-
4b	83	3266 (-OH), 2118 (C=C), 1655 (C=O)	1.16 (2H, t, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz), 2.57 (6H, t, <i>J</i> 7.5 Hz), 3.04 (3H, q, <i>J</i> 7.5 Hz), 4.75 (4H, d, <i>J</i> 7.5 Hz), 6.66 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 9.5 Hz), 6.72 (1H, s), 7.82 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 9.5 Hz)	-
5a	70	3404 (-OH), 1675 (C=O), 1165, 1033	2.44 (3H, s), 2.64 (3H, s), 6.57 (1H, s), 6.93 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 9.5 Hz), 7.61 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 9.5 Hz), 10.75 (1H, s, D ₂ O exe)	M ⁺ 190 (15), 175 (22), 147 (6), 132 (13), 43 (100)
5b	99	3418 (-OH), 1680 (C=O), 1163, 1035	1.20 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz), 2.40 (3H, s), 2.95 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 7.5 Hz), 6.24 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 9.5 Hz), 6.51 (1H, s), 7.51 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 9.5 Hz), 10.75 (1H, D ₂ O exe)	M ⁺ 204 (12), 189 (20), 161 (8), 146 (18)
6a	120	1674 (C=O), 1150, 1035	2.46 (3H s), 2.62 (3H, s), 2.83 (3H, s), 6.41 (1H, s), 6.62 (1H, s), 7.91 (1H, s)	M ⁺ 228 (10), 213 (19), 185 (8), 170 (17), 43 (100)
6b	113	1680 (C=O), 1154, 1034	1.26 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz), 2.48 (6H, s), 3.17 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 7.5 Hz), 6.41 (1H, s), 6.62 (1H, s), 7.85 (1H, s)	M ⁺ 242 (10), 227 (24), 199 (7), 184 (21)

5a 800 mg (Pet. ether eluate); 5b 750 mg (Pet. ether eluate); 6a 500 mg (Pet. ether : benzene 1 : 1 eluate); 6b 500 mg (Pet. ether : benzene 1 : 1 eluate).

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